

1 Implementation of the ISO 4037:2019 standard using voltage
2 dividers and X-ray spectrometry

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10 Abstract

11 The ISO 4037:2019 standard is the reference standard for dosimetry laboratories who wish to realise dosimet-
12 ric operational quantities for radiation protection calibrations. In implementing the ISO 4037:2019 standard,
13 the X-ray radiation qualities need to be defined according to strict requirements on the material and thickness
14 of the additional filtration, and according to metrologically traceable high voltage bias applied to the X-ray
15 tube. This enables usage of standardized conversion coefficient from air kerma to operational quantities.
16 However, the tube potential may vary as a function of tube current if a protective resistor is built into the
17 protective tube housing, which, if not corrected, alters the energy distributions of the reference field and
18 thus the value of the appropriate conversion coefficients. Particularly at low energies, the energy dependence
19 of the conversion coefficients can be sharp and, depending on the specific realisation of a radiation quality,
20 the conversion coefficient from air kerma to dose equivalent can vary substantially. We have investigated
21 the correspondence between the tube voltage measurements of a X-ray system based on calibrated voltage
22 dividers and that of an X-ray spectrometer system based on a CdTe detector in order to obtain an estimation
23 of the resistance of the protective resistor that is usually unknown. A method based on X-ray spectrometry
24 for calibration of the tube potential even in the presence of tube with protective resistor is presented. Fi-
25 nally, conversion coefficients were calculated using simulated spectra to study the influence of the protective
26 resistor on the determination of these coefficients. The simulated spectra obtained from X-ray tube with
27 and without a protective resistor resulted in differences in conversion coefficients mostly less than 2% but
28 5.6% for the radiation quality considered at the lowest energy.

1 INTRODUCTION

The realization of the current operational quantities in radiation protection dosimetry, *e.g.* the personal or ambient dose equivalent, currently relies on the realization of the air kerma and the use of calculated conversion coefficients to convert the physical quantity of air kerma to the dosimetric operational quantity of choice. The standard ISO 4037 [1, 2, 3] defines the criteria for the realization of radiation qualities in radiation protection dosimetry. These operational quantities are defined to provide a conservative estimate of the quantity effective dose, which cannot be determined experimentally. For most laboratories who may not have access to X-ray spectrometry techniques, the recommended implementation of the ISO 4037:2019 standard is that of 'matched fields' [1]. This requires tight control over both the filter material, purity and thickness, and the use of voltage dividers with a traceable calibration, the ISO recommended method to determine the voltage applied to the X-ray tube. The voltage dividers, however, must be used with caution as although they may, when calibrated, correctly indicate the voltage that is downstream to the high voltage supply, they may not indicate the voltage that is effectively available on the X-ray tube. In fact, the ISO 4037:2019 part 1 in section 4.2.2 states that the tube potential (potential difference between cathode and anode of the X-ray tube) is not always equal to the generating potential (the potential difference between the high voltage electrical connections of the protective housing of the X-ray tube). The former can be smaller, if a protective resistor is built into the protective tube housing, causing a voltage drop. In addition, the difference between these two voltages would then also depend on the tube current. It is important to know from the manufacturer of the protective tube housing whether such a protective resistor is installed. Unfortunately, information about the protective resistor is not always easy to obtain from the manufacturer and, if present, its exact value is unknown to the user.

To overcome these difficulties, we propose to determine the potential difference between anode and cathode with a non-invasive method, by estimating the endpoint energy of an X-ray spectrum from the measured pulse-height spectrum. A measurement of the maximum photon energy (E_{\max}) with a spectrometer is performed, and the tube potential can be obtained with equation $V = E_{\max}/e$, where e is the elementary charge.

Other authors proposed a spectrometric method for the determination of the spectrum endpoint energy based on the comparison of the shape of the end part of the measured detector spectra to those of the Monte Carlo simulated detector spectra [4]. This method requires that a Monte Carlo model of the detector must be available and validated, and charge carrier transport (CCT) plus Gaussian Energy Broadening (GEB) valid in the appropriate count-rate regime should be applied on the simulated detector spectrum.

60 The ISO 4037:2019 standard mentions that the protective resistor is usually in the order of 100 k Ω . As
61 an example, this means that, at a nominal tube current of 20 mA, the tube potential is reduced by 2 kV as
62 compared to the generating potential. This reduction, if not corrected, alters the energy distribution of the
63 reference field and may have an impact on the value of the appropriate conversion coefficients. Therefore, the
64 tube voltage needs to be corrected to compensate for the voltage drop due to the protective resistor, when
65 this is present. The voltage drop across this resistor shall then be determined in order to set the desired
66 tube potential.

67 After the publication of the ISO 4037:2019 standard, several laboratories faced the problems caused by
68 the presence of the protective resistor on their tube which, if present in their installation, would make the
69 acquisition of voltage dividers only half useful. Some laboratories just verify the presence of the protective
70 resistor studying the linearity of the air kerma rate as a function of the current in the X-ray tube [5], and
71 other authors use a high purity germanium (HPGe) spectrometer to acquire the pulse height spectrum and
72 obtain the spectrum endpoint energy showing a variation in the voltage as a function of tube current [7].

73 In this work, we want to show the effects that the presence of the protective resistor produces and
74 provide a method to estimate the value of the protective resistor using a CdTe spectrometer. The CdTe
75 spectrometer is arguably more affordable than a HPGe spectrometer, as well as more practical because the
76 small dimensions make transport and positioning in the beam relatively simple.

77 Importantly, no spectrum unfolding procedure is needed for the endpoint energy estimation. The goal
78 of unfolding is the reconstruction of the undisturbed fluence spectrum which would prevail at the location
79 of the detector if the detector was taken away. To remove detector effects from a measured spectrum, the
80 photon response of the detector has to be known as precisely as possible [19].

81 The shape of the undisturbed photon fluence spectrum is not important when the interest is in the
82 endpoint energy of the radiation spectrum. This makes this procedure and the use of the spectrometer
83 relatively easy, and a laboratory can apply this procedure without particular trouble in collecting and
84 analysing data.

85 Furthermore, we want to propose a useful and accessible alternative solution for those laboratories that
86 cannot afford the purchase costs of the voltage divider and its subsequent re-calibrations, which also can
87 impact the running costs.

88 Our study shows that the method developed in our institute, based on the measurement of highly filtered
89 spectra using a CdTe spectrometer, allows the tube potential as a function of tube current to be calibrated
90 on site even in the presence of a protective resistor in the X-ray tube. With the proposed method, knowing

91 the shape of the fluence spectrum is not necessary, so there is no need to unfold the measured pulse-height
92 spectra. However, knowledge of the spectrometer energy calibration, and the energy resolution, is necessary.
93 To support our point, we have investigated the correspondence between the readings of a system based on
94 calibration voltage dividers and that of an energy-calibrated X-ray spectrometer system based on a CdTe
95 detector. In quantifying the differences, we estimate the uncertainties associated with the implementation
96 of the ISO 4037:2019 standard when relying on the use of calibrated voltage dividers and when the effects
97 of the protective resistor are not properly taken into account. Finally, an estimation of several conversion
98 coefficients $h_K^*(10; N)$ is presented to quantify the implication of using a different voltage value due to the
99 presence of the protective resistor in the X-ray system.

100 The criticality of the issue is that if a laboratory is unable to purchase and maintain the voltage dividers,
101 they do not comply with the current standard and the radiation protection calibration would not be recog-
102 nized and accepted by regulatory bodies. The results presented here provide a basis for developing updated
103 recommendations in this area.

104 2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

105 2.1 Irradiation facilities

106 Measurements were made in two metrology laboratories: the Italian National Institute of Ionizing Radiation
107 Metrology (ENEA-INMRI), and the Secondary Standard Dosimetry Laboratory of the Finnish Radiation
108 and Nuclear Safety Authority (STUK). ENEA-INMRI is the Italian primary standards dosimetry laboratory
109 (PSDL) for ionizing radiation quantities. Concerning the kilovoltage X-ray energies, a fairly wide range of
110 qualities are available for medical, industrial and radiation protection purposes. In this study, measurements
111 at ENEA-INMRI were carried out on a bipolar ISOVOLT (called ENEA-INMRI X-ray tube in this work)
112 manufactured by GE and equipped with two GE 225 kV high voltage (HV) generators. Both high voltage
113 generators are complemented by calibrated voltage dividers manufactured by WayGate Technologies. The
114 X-ray tube has a built-in protective resistor. The divided voltage signal was read either by a high impedance
115 calibrated electrometer or sent to an oscilloscope for analysis of the high voltage ripple. The calibration
116 certificate of each divider was issued with MRA-ILAC compliance upon first purchase of the equipment.

117 The secondary standards dosimetry laboratory of STUK is the Finnish designated metrology institute
118 that maintains national measurement standards for ionizing radiation. The laboratory has two different
119 industrial X-ray systems, a low energy tube GE, ISOVOLT TITAN 160 kV (called STUK low energy tube in

120 this work) and a GE, ISOVOLT TITAN 320 kV (called STUK medium energy tube in this work). The STUK
121 X-ray tubes do not have a protective resistor. There are no voltage dividers installed on the high voltage
122 generators at STUK. However, a voltage divider was rented for a short period of time to get traceable
123 voltage measurement for the STUK low energy tube. The constancy of the generator voltage output is
124 checked regularly with HPGe spectrometry measurements, and during calibrations with a monitor chamber;
125 deviations smaller than 0.1 kV in the tube voltage would be visible in the spectrum, and deviations in voltage
126 higher than the limits given by ISO 4037 would cause a change in the monitor chamber reading higher than
127 the tolerance set by the laboratory. The voltage determination for the STUK medium energy tube is based
128 on spectrometry measurements only.

129 **2.2 X-ray Spectrometer**

130 The spectrometer used for this study is a commercial spectrometer X-123 CdTe (AmpTek/AMETEK). The
131 electronics and cooling system together with the sensor are contained in a single small housing that fits in the
132 palm of a hand. The spectrometer is equipped with a collimation system, including a hollow brass cylinder
133 which can house several tungsten collimators inside. The aim of the collimation system is to reduce the
134 fluence of incident X-rays to allow the electronics to process the spectrum by limiting the effects of pile-up
135 of counts. The instrument was supplied with five tungsten collimators with nominal diameters ranging from
136 25 μm to 2000 μm . If a measurement of photon fluence was sought, a verification of the actual aperture
137 diameters would be necessary, as in [5]. For our measurements, we used a stack made of three collimators with
138 nominal diameters 2 mm, 1 mm and 400 μm going from the X-ray tube to the detector entrance surface. The
139 spectrometer is positioned in the beam and the collimator aperture is aligned along the direction parallel
140 to the longitudinal beam axis with a laser pointer. For a measurement of endpoint energy, the correct
141 alignment of the CdTe detector in the photon beam is not as crucial as it would be for the determination
142 of the photon fluence spectrum. Any scatter from a misaligned collimator set would affect the shape of the
143 fluence spectrum but not its endpoint energy.

144 **2.3 Energy calibration and detector energy resolution**

145 The energy calibration of the CdTe spectrometer was achieved using low activity point sources from the
146 radioactivity division of ENEA-INMRI. The sources used when calibrating the detector were ^{241}Am , ^{133}Ba ,
147 ^{152}Eu and ^{57}Co , and the calibration was checked at STUK with ^{133}Ba and ^{57}Co sources. The activities of
148 these sources was chosen so as to keep the detector count rate below 10,000 s^{-1} .

149 For the energy calibration, the user is assisted by a purposely-developed Python script which offers
150 an automated calibration procedure. Information on the energy 'peaks' to be sought using a CdTe type
151 detector, for each nuclide, are stored in an ASCII file nuclide library which is consulted by the Python
152 script to mark a correspondence between the centroid of an energy peak and its energy value. The user
153 can apply such a procedure on the raw spectrum, i.e. with no need to apply any corrections towards the
154 elimination of all distorting effects that are caused by all interaction events in the CdTe that deviate from
155 a full-energy absorption, which greatly simplifies the procedure. For the automated recognition of the peak
156 centroid, a simplified approach relying on automated search of Gaussian peaks is used (Python library
157 module: SciPy) where the user must define some parameters that facilitate the automated recognition of the
158 peaks. This simplification does not take into account incomplete charge collection that is known to affect
159 this type of semiconductor based detectors [5, 6, 13] and that is energy-dependent. However, the effect of
160 this simplification is small and limited to a maximum deviation of 0.4 keV [6] at the largest energies of
161 interest in X-ray dosimetry for radiation protection, and, in line with the scope of this work of providing a
162 practical method to implement the ISO 4037:2019 standard. The energy calibration is provided as output
163 and a linear function was chosen.

164 The same calibration spectra were used to measure the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the CdTe
165 detector in the energy range from 10 keV to 140 keV. A gaussian fit was performed on the selected peak and
166 the standard deviation obtained as fit parameter was used to obtain the peak's FWHM using the relation
167 $FWHM = 2.35 \cdot \sigma$ [16]. In some cases, multiple peaks are very close (e.g. 79.6142 keV and 80.9979 keV for
168 ^{133}Ba [17], for example) and the use of a Gaussian fit function will lead to an incorrect standard deviation;
169 in these cases, the used peak's fit function was a sum of two Gaussians with the same standard deviation
170 but different centroids.

171 To fit the FWHM in function of the peak's energy the function used is $FWHM [keV] = a + \sqrt{b \cdot E [keV]}$.
172 Results are shown in Figure 1.

173 This analysis was done using SciPy Python's library module.

174 **2.4 Experimental set-up**

175 For each described X-ray tube apparatus, we used the experimental setup as reported in Figure 2. Our
176 measurements are geared toward characterising the output of the tubes with validation provided not only
177 by the dividers but especially by the spectrometer.

178 As it is well known, all the constant voltage power supplies, either linear or switching-mode, present a

Figure 1: Fit of the measured energy resolution with CdTe detector.

Figure 2: Graphic layout of the experimental set-up.

179 constant voltage mean value with superimposed small oscillations produced in the rectifying process, with a
180 frequency of hundreds of Hz or tens or hundreds of kHz. These variations were experimentally investigated
181 by means of oscilloscope measurements and estimated in order to understand their effects on the position of
182 the spectrum energy endpoint. The distance of the CdTe detector from the focus was increased with higher
183 tube currents in order to reduce the fluence of incident photons, and thus the pile-up.

184 A measurement of the cathode current is inferred from a voltage measurement that is taken from a circuit
185 board inside the power supply of the x-ray tube. Throughout all experimental sessions, the digital console
186 (reporting the actual measured current rather than the nominal set-point) showed no observable fluctuations.
187 In light of these technical characteristics, the uncertainty associated with the tube current was considered
188 negligible.

189 For all qualities studied at ENEA and STUK we added filtration (aluminium, tin, copper, and lead)
190 to standard qualities in order to reduce the fluence and decrease the electronic pile-up. The filters applied
191 modify the shape of the spectrum as they selectively cut the low energy part (beam hardening) but the
192 objective of this study is not to determine the shape of the fluence spectrum, but rather its energy endpoint.
193 Thus, the pulse-height spectra, obtained from the filtration, are relatively narrow and present a steep descent
194 in the terminal part of the spectrum. The beam hardening, achieved with the additional filters, implies a
195 reduction of the photon fluence, which means a lower dead time and a negligible electronic pile-up from the
196 CdTe detector point of view. Finally, using the SpekPy toolkit [10], different fluence spectra were simulated
197 to study the variation of the conversion coefficient h_K^* with respect to the potential between anode and
198 cathode voltage divider reading and corrected value from spectrometry.

199 **2.4.1 Endpoint energy estimation**

200 The endpoint energy was determined from the measured pulse-height spectrum using two complementary
201 methods. In the first method, the background radiation level is assumed to be approximately constant.
202 The spectrum endpoint is identified as the intersection between a linear fit of the high-energy tail and the
203 horizontal line representing the mean background. A typical problem with this method is the choice of the
204 ideal energy range in which to perform the linear regression. The linear regression is first performed in
205 the energy range (A_{\min}, A_{\max}) where A_{\max} is an energy value near the endpoint energy and $A_{\min} < A_{\max}$
206 such that there are at least 10 energy bins between A_{\min} and A_{\max} and the R^2 coefficient of the linear
207 regression is stored. Several iterations are made varying A_{\min} moving one step towards low energy. The
208 whole procedure is repeated by varying the value A_{\max} . The selected energy range was chosen so to maximize

Figure 3: (a) Raw spectrum at 60 kV (N60 X-ray beam quality). (b) Exploded view of the high-energy region of the same raw spectrum (a) showing the endpoints obtained by applying the two methods.

209 the R^2 coefficient, spectrum tail and linear fit in the selected energy range are plotted so that the operator
 210 can check the results.

211 The second method, instead, is based on the estimation of the measured background and the energy
 212 resolution of the detector. An estimation of the mean background counts (C_b) is obtained from the measured
 213 background spectrum; then an algorithm starting from the spectrum high energy region searches the first
 214 channel with a number of counts (C) such that $C > 3C_b + 3$. We have chosen the value $3C_b$ because we
 215 assume the background counts have a Gaussian distribution with C_b as mean value. Knowing the standard
 216 deviation, we find that the value $3C_b$ has a probability to occur $< 0.01\%$ to lie within the background. In
 217 this way we are confident that the number of counts $C > 3C_b$ are generated by photons from the X-ray tube.

218 At this point, the peak broadening caused by spectrometer energy resolution must be considered. Apply-
 219 ing the second method to a mono-energetic peak, assuming the peak has a Gaussian shape, it leads to a value
 220 on the high energy tail instead of its centroid. To bring the estimated endpoint to the centroid, knowing the
 221 FWHM(E) as function of the energy, a value equal to $\text{FWHM}(E)/2$ is subtracted from the obtained high
 222 energy tail value. In this way, we correct the energy endpoint estimated with the second method.

223 In the present work, the endpoint is evaluated using both methods, yielding two distinct values, as shown
 224 in Figure 3 for the case of 60 kV (N60 as in ISO 4037 [1]).

225 Since there is no pre-knowledge regarding the probability distribution associated with the endpoint energy,
 226 a conservative approach was chosen based on a uniform-type distribution. Since the two methods are
 227 consistently defining an interval, with one method always over-estimating the other, the values obtained
 228 from the two methods are used as extremes of the uniform distribution. We assume that the real value of
 229 the endpoint energy is uniformly distributed within the range of these estimated values, and we obtain the

230 final endpoint energy as the mean value of this distribution with its standard deviation.

231 **3 Results**

232 **3.0.1 HV generators ripple estimation**

233 As already mentioned in the previous section, voltage power supplies present a constant voltage mean value
234 with superimposed small oscillations from rectifying processes, with a frequency of hundreds of Hz or tens
235 or hundreds of kHz. These voltage oscillations are in the range of kV, varying the voltage difference between
236 anode and cathode. These variations were experimentally investigated and estimated in order to understand
237 their effects on the position of the energy spectrum endpoint. It has been found out, by an oscilloscope, that
238 the ripple oscillations of the positive voltage supply connected to the anode are equal to and in phase with
239 the ripple oscillations of the negative voltage supply connected to the cathode. This is possible because the
240 two voltage power supplies are switching-mode with synchronised inverter oscillators at 17 kHz. Therefore,
241 the two ripples cancel each other out.

242 However, the two ripple signals possessed also several overshoots at several hundreds of kHz which are
243 conversely in phase opposition and hence they do not cancel out but they add up instead, and, together
244 with the HV mean values, can produce a slight increase of the HV difference and hence shift the spectrum
245 endpoint to slightly higher energies. While the ripple period is about 60 μs , the duration of the overshoots is
246 about 2 μs . This means that the upward parts of the overshoot ringing last about 1 μs or a bit less. Because
247 of this short time, the question was raised as to whether the electrons that fly from the cathode to the anode
248 have the time be affected by these voltage overshoots.

249 An easy estimation of the time of flight of the electrons which are accelerated by the voltage difference
250 between the anode and the cathode showed that this time of flight is in the order of few nano seconds.
251 Therefore, the electrons are indeed affected by these voltage overshoots which make their kinetic energy
252 increase and thus can cause a shift of the spectrum endpoint. The height of these overshoots was measured
253 by an oscilloscope and turned out to vary between 300 and 500 volts. Besides, the temporal weight of the
254 overshoots was also estimated by comparing their duration with the ripple period in order to have an idea
255 of how much these “over accelerated” electrons may contribute to shift the energy endpoint of the X-ray
256 spectrum. In the end it appears that the possible shift of the endpoint towards higher energies lies within
257 the uncertainty in determining the endpoint position.

Figure 4: Data obtained from ENEA-INMRI voltage dividers and CdTe spectrometer as function of current for 60 kV nominal voltage case. The voltage values measured with voltage dividers are indicated as points with their uncertainties of 0.25% ($k=1$). The endpoint energy values calculated from spectrometry measurements are shown as crosses with their uncertainties of 1.5% ($k=1$), see section **Uncertainty budget**. The grey band represents the acceptable range criteria.

258 3.1 Voltage calibration and protective resistor

259 The results, obtained with the methods described in the previous section, provide two strategies for the HV
 260 calibration of a X-ray tube both with and without the protective resistor.

261 The first scenario refers to the X-ray tube equipped with the protective resistor (ENEA-INMRI X-ray
 262 tube). In this case, the endpoint energy evaluated from the measured X-ray spectrum is the proposed method
 263 to determine the high voltage difference applied between anode and cathode. As an example, the results for
 264 the nominal voltage of 60 kV are plotted in Figure 4 and reported in Table 1. Figure 4 shows the voltage
 265 values measured with voltage dividers and the endpoint energy values as function of current. It can be
 266 observed that to achieve a certain tube voltage value of 60 kV, we compensate the tube voltage setting on
 267 the console so that the measured endpoint falls within the acceptable range around the desired potential.
 268 The acceptable range was chosen to be ± 0.5 kV.

269 From spectrum endpoint estimations, the tube voltage was stable within 0.3 kV while the voltage divider
 270 result varied from 60.7 kV to 67.0 kV. This means that if one is not aware of the presence of the tube
 271 protective resistor, a significant voltage difference may be applied between cathode and anode as the current

Table 1: Values for 60 kV nominal voltage with the ENEA-INMRI X-ray tube equipped with the protective resistor. The data are shown in Figure 4.

Anode current (mA)	Voltage divider		Endpoint	
	reading (kV)	uncertainty $k=1$ (kV)	reading (kV)	uncertainty $k=1$ (kV)
1	60.7	0.1	59.7	0.9
5	61.2	0.1	59.9	0.9
10	61.9	0.1	59.8	0.9
15	62.4	0.1	59.6	0.9
20	64.0	0.1	59.8	0.9
30	64.9	0.1	59.8	0.9
45	67.0	0.1	59.7	0.9

272 increases (e.g. 10% at 45 mA for 60 kV). Spectrometry provides a downstream measurement of the X-ray
 273 output which is not accessible to a measurement using a voltage divider.

274 Applying a linear fit $a \cdot x + b$ to the voltage divider data as a function of the current, the slope of the
 275 best-fit line estimates the protective resistance value and this parameter is provided with an uncertainty due
 276 to the linear fit, Figure 5. The protective resistor value for this tube is estimated to be approximately 150
 277 $k\Omega$, in reasonable agreement with the approximate value of 100 $k\Omega$ indicated in the ISO 4037 [1].

278 Knowing the value of the protective resistance R , we are able to quantify the potential drop and com-
 279 pensate the console settings for it in order to obtain the desired voltage V_{nominal} expressed in kV between
 280 anode and cathode, using this simple relation

$$V_{\text{divider}} = V_{\text{nominal}} + R \cdot c \quad (1)$$

281 where V_{divider} refers to the voltage dividers measurement, R is the resistance, and c is the current.

282 To verify the estimated resistance value, we repeated the measurements at a different nominal voltage.
 283 The voltage selected is 135 kV because, due to the power limits of ENEA-INMRI generators, moving to
 284 larger voltage values could limit the current range which, in fact, we wish to keep as large as possible to
 285 demonstrate the effectiveness of the approach. We use equation 1 to calculate the value $R \cdot c$ in order to
 286 obtain V_{divider} for a fixed desired voltage value between anode and cathode. The results are shown in Table
 287 2 and plotted in Figure 6.

288 The obtained voltage values, reported in Table 2, were stable within 0.5 kV while the voltage divider
 289 result varied from 135.1 kV to 138.3 kV. This demonstrates that the tube potential is stable with a very low
 290 deviation.

Figure 5: Linear fit of ENEA-INMRI voltage divider reading compensated by the potential drop due to the protective resistor for 60 kV desired voltage. Experimental data and their uncertainties are presented in Table 1.

Figure 6: Extrapolated data analysis from ENEA-INMRI X-ray tube, thanks to spectrometer method, as a function of current for 135 kV desired voltage. The uncertainties reported in the plot are the spectrum endpoint total uncertainties ($k=1$), see section **Uncertainty budget**. Dotted line represents the desired voltage value.

Table 2: Values for 135 kV nominal voltage with a X-ray tube equipped with the protective resistor. The data are shown in Figure 6.

Anode current (mA)	Voltage drop $R \cdot c$ (kV)	Endpoint (kV)	Endpoint uncertainty k=1 (kV)
10	1.5	135.2	2.0
15	2.2	135.3	2.0
20	2.9	135.5	2.0
25	3.7	135.1	2.0
32	4.7	135.6	2.0

291 These results show that the estimated resistance value is consistent and, using equation 1, we can predict
 292 the voltage divider reading to be set to obtain the desired voltage value that is effectively applied between
 293 tube anode and cathode.

294 Similar measurements were performed in July 2023 at STUK. As described in the previous sections, both
 295 X-ray systems have no protective resistor and no voltage dividers are permanently installed in the facility.

296 The voltages for both X-ray tubes were set close to 60 kV. Voltage values were fixed, and for the ENEA-
 297 INMRI X-ray tube the anode current varied in the range 0.5-30 mA, and for the low-energy tube from 0.5
 298 mA to 45 mA.

299 In Figure 7, it can be seen that the generating potential, obtained with the spectrometry method, does
 300 not depend on the current for both tubes. Considering the ENEA-INMRI X-ray tube, the obtained voltage
 301 values were stable within 0.5 kV, while for low energy tube, the obtained voltage values were stable within
 302 0.7 kV. The results confirm that no protective resistor is installed in either STUK X-ray tubes, and the
 303 generating potential and tube potential are consistent and independent of tube current. The endpoint values
 304 obtained by the presented method are in agreement, within the uncertainty, with those obtained by STUK.

305 3.2 Uncertainty budget

306 An analysis of uncertainty components was performed, following the international guidance [9]. Here, all
 307 uncertainties presented are relative standard uncertainties, at coverage factor k=1.

308 Each ENEA-INMRI calibrated voltage divider system has an estimated uncertainty of 0.25% (k=1).
 309 Since the ENEA-INMRI X-ray tube has two generators we need two voltage dividers, each one with its
 310 calibration coefficient and its electrometer, then the total uncertainty is given by using the general formula
 311 for uncertainty propagation.

312 Analysis of the influence on uncertainty of the spectrometer energy calibration curve and energy resolution

Figure 7: Top, results from STUK low energy X-ray tube. Bottom, results from STUK medium energy X-ray tube. The uncertainties reported in the plots are the spectrum endpoint total uncertainties ($k=1$), see section **Uncertainty budget**.

Table 3: Uncertainty budget related to the endpoint energy determination at $k=1$.

Source of uncertainty	Relative uncertainty (%)
Energy calibration stability in time	0.18
Energy calibration curve	0.12
Energy resolution (FWHM)	0.44
Background	0.08
Counting statistic	0.07
Method 1	1.33
Method 2	0.17
Rectangular distribution	0.33
Combined standard uncertainty	1.5

313 was performed by varying the number of the X and γ lines considered in the calibration and energy resolution
 314 estimation. Spectra from the radioactive sources were combined in a set of 2, 3 or 4 sources, in order to obtain
 315 between 4 and 7 lines for the calibration and energy resolution estimation. Using the energy calibrations
 316 performed over two years, it was possible to assess the uncertainty due to the temporal stability of the energy
 317 calibration procedure.

318 Several background spectra were measured in order to use them to estimate the uncertainty due to
 319 the background on the estimated endpoint energy. The proposed method for estimating the spectrum
 320 endpoint energy was applied using these background spectra, and this component of the uncertainty was
 321 thus estimated.

322 To estimate the uncertainty related to Method 2, endpoints are obtained by first choosing a smaller and
 323 then a larger channel than the one selected by the algorithm and the semi-range between these two values
 324 provides an estimate of the uncertainty.

325 The Monte Carlo method was used to estimate the uncertainty associated to Method 1 and counting
 326 statistics according to the Guide for expression of Uncertainty in Measurements [14]. It consists of varying
 327 each quantity within its uncertainty 10000 times and estimating the endpoint energy each time to obtain
 328 the effect of variation of the endpoint energy value. The distribution of endpoint energy values gives a
 329 gaussian shape and its width obtained by a fit procedure is taken as uncertainty for the component under
 330 consideration.

331 Table 3 summarises the values obtained for each uncertainty component. All uncertainty components are
 332 assumed to be uncorrelated and are summed in quadrature to obtain an estimate of the combined standard
 333 uncertainty.

334 The resistor value was obtained using a linear least-square fitting procedure with a linear function on

335 voltage divider readings with their uncertainties as function of current. The fit parameters were estimated
 336 with their uncertainties [15] and the resistor uncertainty u_R is 2% ($k=1$).

337 From equation 1, using the general formula for relative uncertainty propagation, we can obtain the desired
 338 voltage V_{nominal} uncertainty in presence of protective resistor.

339 **3.3 Implications on conversion coefficients $h_k^*(10)$**

340 The voltage characterization of an X-ray system has an influence on the determination of radiation qualities
 341 and conversion factors for calibration services. A sensitivity analysis of the conversion coefficients from air
 342 kerma to the quantity ambient dose equivalent $H^*(10)$ is presented below to understand whether the accu-
 343 racy of spectrometry-based measurements of spectral endpoint energy is sufficient for radiation protection
 344 dosimetry applications. Starting from a ionisation chamber calibrated in terms of air kerma K_a , one can
 345 obtain a measurement of $H^*(10)$ using the conversion coefficients.

346 The simulated X-ray tube used in SpekPy has a tungsten target with a 20 degrees anode angle and a 3
 347 mm thick beryllium window. N-60 filter was composed by 4.02 mm of aluminium and 0.61 mm of copper.
 348 The spectrometer was positioned 100 cm from the focus along the beam axis. To allow for air attenuation,
 349 an additional filter made of air with thickness of 100 cm was added. Two fluence spectra were simulated:
 350 in the first simulation we assumed no protective resistor in the tube and we set the tube potential equal to
 351 the voltage divider readout of 60 kV; in the second case we took into account a lower high voltage value,
 352 consequence of the voltage drop explained and demonstrated earlier, occurring in an X-ray tube with a
 353 protective resistor. We experimentally found the value of the protective resistor and the potential between
 354 anode and cathode was calculated using equation 1. As we discussed in the previous paragraph, when the
 355 divider read-out is 60.0 kV, the effective potential measured is 57.1 kV for a tube current of 20 mA. This two
 356 voltage values are the tube potentials chosen for the comparison. Simulated spectra are shown in Figure 8.

357 Spectrum averaged values of the conversion coefficients were calculated by simulated fluence spectra
 358 with the corresponding conversion coefficient from K_a to $H^*(10)$ for mono-energetic photons $h_K^*(10; E)$, as
 359 tabulated in ISO 4037:2019-3 chapter 6.3 [3]. The conversion coefficient $h_K^*(10; N)$ for the narrow series
 360 N-60 is obtained using the following equation:

$$h_K^*(10; N) = \frac{\int_{E_{\min}}^{E_{\max}} \Phi_E(E) \cdot k_{\Phi}(E) \cdot h_K^*(10; E) dE}{\int_{E_{\min}}^{E_{\max}} \Phi_E(E) \cdot k_{\Phi}(E) dE} \quad (2)$$

361 where $k_{\Phi}(E) = E \cdot \frac{\mu_{\text{en}}(E)}{\rho}$ represents the energy dependent kerma factors, with mass energy-absorption

Figure 8: SpekPy N-60 simulated spectra for different tube potentials.

362 coefficient $\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}(E)}{\rho}$ values for mono-energetic photons in dry air taken from Hubbell et al. [11] and interpolated
 363 between two points, $\Phi_E(E)$ is the fluence, while E_{min} and E_{max} are the energy limits of the adopted fluence
 364 spectra.

365 The calculated values of ambient dose equivalent for each of the two spectra are reported in Table 4. The
 366 conversion coefficients differ by 1.54% for the two simulated spectra.

367 Simulations for several X-ray ISO 4037:2019 qualities implemented in our laboratories were performed
 368 for a sensitivity analysis of the conversion coefficients. A current of 20 mA was assumed for all qualities,
 369 leading to a fixed compensation of 2.94 kV as in equation 1, to compensate for the presence of the protective
 370 resistor. Conversion coefficients were calculated for each quality from the simulated spectra obtained by first
 371 using the potential difference read by the voltage divider and then using that obtained from spectrometry;
 372 results are summarised in Table 4.

373 The corrections are relevant mostly for low potential values, indeed a significant difference higher than 4%
 374 is observed for the ISO quality N-40. The effect is larger with lower voltage qualities. The reason for this is
 375 the sensitivity of the spectrum shape to small changes in the voltage and the large gradient of monoenergetic
 376 conversion coefficients at low energies, as provided in [3].

377 The data we presented here are an example and we did not check the effect of voltage drop below 40
 378 kV generating potential since this is the lowest high voltage value in use at ENEA-INMRI with the 450 kV

Table 4: Conversion coefficients, $h_k^*(10)$, in case of nominal potential and a lowered potential by 2.94 kV and the percentage difference between them. The values were calculated for several X-ray qualities using simulated spectra by means of SpekPy.

ISO quality	$h_k^*(10)$ from voltage divider (Sv/Gy)	$h_k^*(10)$ corrected (Sv/Gy)	percentage difference (%)
N-40	1.18	1.12	5.64
N-60	1.58	1.56	1.54
N-80	1.73	1.72	0.04
N-100	1.72	1.72	0.02
N-120	1.72	1.72	0.00
W-60	1.49	1.47	1.70
W-80	1.64	1.64	0.52

379 X-ray tube under investigation. In addition, we chose an unique 20 mA tube current value because this
 380 value allows calibrations to be performed in a reasonably short time and it's a typical current value used in
 381 measurements with several instruments.

382 In light of these results, the majority of the estimated values of the conversion coefficients h_K^* are in
 383 agreement within an uncertainty of 4% for $k=2$ with the values reported in the ISO 4037:2019 standard.
 384 The presence of the protective resistor does not significantly modify the values of the coefficients for the
 385 N-series qualities with tube voltage higher than 60 kV. For the N-40 quality, the presence of the protective
 386 resistor introduces an uncertainty greater than 4%, so that, in this case, it is essential to know of the presence
 387 of a protective resistor to obtain the effective potential difference between anode and cathode.

388 4 Conclusion

389 One of the questions facing the community of ionizing radiation metrology institutes at this time, be these
 390 Primary or Secondary Standards Laboratories, is if spectrometry could be accepted in the future in place of
 391 calibrated voltage dividers as the recommended method to determine the X-ray tube potential according to
 392 the ISO 4037:2019 standard. The determination of the spectrum endpoint energy has been investigated by
 393 Šolc et al [4] and many studies are underway on the topic [7, 8] with measurement campaigns set up with
 394 different type of spectrometers, voltage dividers, and multimeter dosimetry systems for reference dosimetry
 395 in diagnostic radiology (X-ray MultiMeters - XMMs [18]).

396 We have shown here how to determine the tube voltage with a CdTe spectrometer and estimate the value
 397 of the resistance of the protective resistor, then using that value to make appropriate corrections to high-
 398 voltage readings based on voltage dividers. The spectrometry method is surely less expensive and accessible

399 to a larger group of laboratories that cannot afford the purchase and periodic calibration of high voltage
400 dividers. Importantly, in this procedure, the spectrometer is used only for endpoint evaluation and so no
401 unfolding data processing is needed [6, 19]. This makes the spectrometry-based approach described here
402 significantly more accessible even to smaller laboratories with a limited experience in spectrometry.

403 We investigated the effect of using an X-ray tube with protective resistor and high voltage dividers on
404 the determination of conversion coefficients from air kerma to $H^*(10)$ using simulated spectra. Differences
405 smaller than 4% for most of the considered radiation qualities were observed.

406 Importantly, under the setup described here, the anode current measurement is not traceable, a limit
407 in the approach described. However, given the effectiveness of the corrections to the voltage value that we
408 made based on the determination of the protective resistance, the lack of traceability in the anode current
409 measurement did not appear to be critical.

410 Future developments will aim at reducing the uncertainty in the determination of the spectrum endpoint
411 energy and in the application of this method to perform calibration in terms of voltage for XMMs which are
412 largely used for quality control tests in diagnostic radiology [18].

413 Authors' Contribution statement

414 Luigi Rinaldi: writing (Original Draft Preparation), conceptualization, formal analysis. Alessia Ciccotelli:
415 writing (review and editing), conceptualization, investigation, supervision. Claudia Silvestri: conceptual-
416 ization, investigation, supervision. Andrea Petrucci: writing (review and editing), investigation. Gianluca
417 Cappadozzi: investigation, software. Susy Toma: investigation (optimization of CdTe settings). Serena
418 Fattori: software (CdTe energy calibration). Parvin Mohammadyari: software (CdTe energy calibration).
419 Francesca Curciarello: writing (review). Joonas Tikkanen: writing (review and editing), conceptualiza-
420 tion, investigation, supervision. Paula Toroi: writing (review and editing), conceptualization, investigation,
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